

DFRT studies of amide-coupled benzoic nitrogen mustard derivatives

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Abstract : Reactivity of aziridinium ion as well as mono-adducts formed during alkylation of DNA (with guanine) by few amide-coupled benzoic nitrogen mustard derivatives are analysed using density functional reactivity theory (DFRT). Global and local reactivity descriptors are used to compare the reactivity of the aziridinium ion intermediates and mono-adducts. Our results clearly explain the reactivity pattern in the species and examined the validity of maximum hardness principle (MHP) and minimum electrophilicity principle (MEP). We reported a strong interaction between aziridinium ion and guanine. Existence of thermodynamic driving forces and the influence of incorporation of the aqueous phase are also examined.

Keywords : DNA cross-linking agents, aziridinium ion, DFT based reactivity descriptors, DFRT, drug DNA adduct.

Introduction

Nitrogen mustards represent the earliest DNA inter-strand cross-linking agents that have been used in cancer chemotherapy since last half century, and plenty of studies reflected their importance as potent chemotherapeutic agents¹. Mustine is the oldest member of this family and one of the most extensively employed chemotherapeutic agents. This class of drug molecules forms a positively charged reactive intermediate which is unstable and can easily react with different nucleophilic centers of cellular molecules like DNA, RNA, proteins etc.². A number of studies confirmed their mechanism of action and alkylation of the DNA bases (preferably at N7 position of guanine) is the favoured mechanism of these drugs to evince their cytotoxicity³, Scheme 1. It was also reported that the alkylation occurs preferentially at the endocyclic nitrogen and exocyclic oxygen atoms of the DNA bases⁴. Among the drug molecules, mustine is the most reactive, due to which, more stable analogues were sought. It is conceivable that substitution of the methyl group of mustine by electron withdrawing groups makes the nitrogen atom less nucleophilic. This slows down the rate of aziridinium ion formation, in turn reducing the reactivity of the drug⁵. In recent years a number of attempts have been made to synthesize such derivatives with enhanced potency⁶. Ben-

zoic nitrogen mustard possessing relatively low toxicity and this class of nitrogen mustard derivative drawn lots of attention⁷. Recently Zheng *et al.* have synthesized a series of amide-coupled benzoic nitrogen mustard derivatives and some of them exhibit significant activity⁸. Herein we have analyzed the reactivity/stability of aziridinium ion and mono-adduct formed by a few of them, Fig. 1. Though these drug molecules interact with DNA (at guanine N7), for the sake of simplicity we have considered the guanine molecule only. Density functional reactivity theory (DFRT) has been used extensively to explain the reactivity pattern of the molecular systems⁹. In DFRT the reactivity descriptors such as global hardness, chemical potential, electrophilicity etc. are applied to describe the reactivity pattern in chemical species. These descriptors have been tested and studied by several research groups and are found to be very useful in rationalizing the reactivity patterns of the molecular systems¹⁰. Here we have made an effort to analyze the reactivity of the considered systems using this theory.

Computational and theoretical details of the reactivity descriptors :

In DFT chemical potential (μ) is defined as the first

Scheme 1. Drug-guanine mono-adduct formation by nitrogen mustards.

Fig. 1. Amide-coupled benzoic nitrogen mustard derivatives.

derivative of the energy with respect to the number of electrons¹¹,

$$\mu = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (1)$$

And global hardness (η)¹² as :

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (2)$$

where, E is the energy and N is the number of electrons of an electronic system at constant external potential, $v(\vec{r})$.

In most of the applications, chemical potential (μ) and global hardness (η) are calculated using finite difference

approximation in terms of IP and EA which leads to the working formulae

$$\mu = \frac{-(IP + EA)}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = \frac{IP - EA}{2} \quad (4)$$

Use of Koopmans' theorem¹³ defines the IP and EA in terms of the energies of highest occupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{HOMO}) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{LUMO}) as :

$$IP = -\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} \quad (5)$$

$$EA = -\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} \quad (6)$$

And therefore, μ and η can be expressed as :

$$\eta = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mu = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (8)$$

Parr and his co-workers proposed electrophilicity (ω) as a measure of electrophilicity of a species¹⁴ as :

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} \quad (9)$$

It is the measure of capacity of a species to accept an arbitrary number of electrons.

The gas phase geometrical minima of the species are obtained using 6-31G(d,p) basis set with B3LYP (Becke three parameter exchange and Lee, Yang and Parr correlation functional)¹⁵ and are confirmed by frequency calculations. The global reactivity descriptors (chemical potential, global hardness and electrophilicity) are calculated using eqs. (7)–(9). All the calculations are carried out using Gaussian09¹⁶.

Results and discussion

Stability of the drug, aziridinium ion and drug-guanine adduct :

Calculated value of the global hardness of the chemical species is presented in Fig. 2. The gas phase trend in global hardness, Fig. 2a, shows that stability of the spe-

cies is in the order : drug > aziridinium ion > drug-guanine. Incorporation of aqueous phase, however imparts significant influence on the stability of the species, Fig. 2b. In aqueous phase all the species are observed to be more stable (hardness increases) as compared to the gas phase. Moreover, trends observed in aqueous phase are different from the gas phase. Thus, the study confer that the aqueous phase plays a very significant role in the stability of species.

We examined the applicability of MHP and MEP, plots of global hardness and electrophilicity of the drug, aziridinium ion and the drug-guanine adducts are presented in Fig. 3. It is interesting to see that in most of the cases, both MHP and MEP are obeyed. Both gas phase as well as solvent phase plots exhibits similarity in their trends. Aziridinium ion of “k-m” drugs are exhibiting maximum stability (maximum hardness) whereas aziridinium ion of “b” is the least stable one. Thus aziridinium ion “b” is expected to be the most reactive species.

Interaction energy :

Interaction energy is a very important tool to measure the strength of interaction between two species. Here we have calculated the interaction energies between the aziridinium ion and guanine using the supermolecular approach. The BSSE corrected energies in both gas and aqueous phases are presented in Table 1. A strong interaction between the two species is observed. In gas phase the interaction energies are ≈ 40 kcal/mol. However, in-

Fig. 2. Plots of global hardness in (a) gas phase and (b) aqueous phase.

(a) Drug (gas phase)

(b) Drug (aqueous phase)

(c) Aziridinium ion (gas phase)

(d) Aziridinium ion (aqueous phase)

(e) Drug-guanine adduct (gas phase)

(f) Drug-guanine adduct (aqueous phase)

Fig. 3. Global hardness and electrophilicity of aziridinium ions and drug-guanine adducts.

corporation of aqueous phase leads to a decrease of the values; still fairly strong interaction is observed (aqueous phase interaction energies are ≈ 33 kcal/mol). Thus, our results indicates a strong interaction during adduct formation. This is very important because cytotoxicity of

these class of chemotherapeutic agents depends on the adduct formation.

Thermochemical analysis :

With an aim to analyze the thermodynamic driving forces involved in aziridinium ion and adduct formation,

Table 1. BSSE corrected interaction energies at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of theory

Entry no. (as in Fig. 1)	ΔE_{int} (in kcal/mol)		BSSE correction (kcal/mol)
	Gas phase	Aqueous phase	
a	-42.55	-33.36	5.26
b	-42.01	-33.15	5.32
c	-42.51	-33.42	5.27
d	-43.07	-33.85	5.20
e	-43.10	-34.01	5.19
f	-42.99	-34.05	5.19
g	-43.50	-33.60	5.23
h	-43.97	-33.80	5.23
i	-43.93	-33.79	5.24
j	-43.65	-32.92	5.01
k	-40.29	-31.71	5.12
l	-40.22	-31.72	5.14
m	-41.11	-32.48	5.19

we have calculated enthalpy and Gibb's free energy for both the steps. Enthalpy and Gibb's free energy for formation of aziridinium ion are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Enthalpy and Gibb's free energy of aziridinium ion formation (in kcal/mol)

Entry no. (as in Fig. 1)	ΔH		ΔG	
	Gas phase	Aqueous phase	Gas phase	Aqueous phase
a	141.05	24.80	134.10	17.75
b	140.44	25.25	133.38	16.60
c	141.05	24.78	133.99	17.71
d	141.67	24.42	134.58	20.68
e	141.84	24.75	134.69	20.43
f	141.61	24.58	134.47	19.45
g	142.55	25.61	135.43	16.86
h	143.32	25.85	136.18	17.17
i	143.26	25.22	136.09	19.19
j	146.47	26.11	139.19	19.75
k	138.15	22.88	130.61	14.81
l	137.94	22.96	130.50	16.44
m	139.07	23.78	131.35	16.94

It is clear from Table 2 that enthalpy as well as Gibb's free energy of aziridinium ion formation is highly endothermic in gas phase, $\Delta H \approx 140$ kcal/mol and $\Delta G \approx 130$ kcal/mol. However, incorporation of aqueous phase reduces these values to $\Delta H \approx 24$ kcal/mol and $\Delta G \approx 16$ kcal/mol. Thus the presence of aqueous phase imparts a

significant impact on aziridinium ion formation. These values are nearly equal to the values obtained for mustine, chlorambucil, melphalan etc.¹⁷. From above it can be concluded that there is no thermodynamic driving forces exist for the aziridinium ion formation.

Enthalpy and Gibb's free energy of adduct formation is much more important and accordingly we have calculated these values, presented in Table 3. Gas phase enthalpy of adduct formations are in the range -42.17 kcal/mol to -45.87 kcal/mol. Incorporation of aqueous phase

Table 3. Enthalpy and Gibb's free energy of adduct formation (in kcal/mol)

Entry no. (as in Fig. 1)	ΔH		ΔG	
	Gas phase	Aqueous phase	Gas phase	Aqueous phase
a	-44.51	-36.18	-63.09	-55.51
b	-44.01	-37.25	-62.04	-51.61
c	-44.46	-36.96	-62.35	-51.41
d	-44.97	-37.10	-63.02	-52.22
e	-44.78	-37.10	-62.95	-51.55
f	-44.86	-36.98	-62.84	-52.67
g	-45.42	-36.97	-63.56	-53.43
h	-45.87	-37.82	-63.86	-51.57
i	-45.83	-37.24	-63.73	-53.92
j	-47.76	-38.02	-65.48	-54.25
k	-42.17	-34.92	-60.09	-51.31
l	-42.09	-35.44	-60.44	-53.45
m	-43.01	-36.90	-60.53	-53.01

drop these values by ~ 10 kcal/mol, and the adduct formation is observed to be exothermic. Similar trends are also observed in case of Gibb's free energies. Enthalpy of adduct formation of these drugs is comparable to the other member of this family (mustine, melphalan, chlorambucil)¹⁸. It is thus conclusive to comment that the drug-guanine adduct formation is enthalpy driven. Presence of aqueous phase influence enormously formation of both aziridinium ion and drug-guanine adduct.

Conclusion

In the present article we have analysed the stability of the few amide-coupled benzoic nitrogen mustards derivatives, corresponding aziridinium ions and drug-guanine adducts. Stability of the species measured in terms of global hardness reveals that the stability of the species is

comparable; aziridinium ions are observed to be more stable over the drug-guanine adduct. The reactivity pattern of the species is found to follow MHP and MEP. Drug-guanine adduct formation is enthalpy driven whereas reverse is observed in case of aziridinium ion formation. Incorporation of aqueous phase imparts significant influence on the stability of the species, interaction energy and adducts formation.

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